

Children with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDD) receive much more than education during in-person school. Schools provide vital health care and therapy services for the 14% of public-school students with IDD. Despite reporting additional parental stress during the COVID-19 pandemic, parents worry about sending their highly vulnerable children with IDD back to school in person. Researchers know that masking, social distancing, and frequent cleaning lessens the spread of COVID-19 in schools; however, more evidence is needed to confirm if these strategies work for children with IDD. This RADx-UP study performed weekly saliva COVID-19 testing to assess the spread of COVID-19 among students and staff in schools working with children with IDD.

WHERE:

Special School District, St. Louis County, Missouri

WHEN?

November 2020 to May 2021

WHO?

475 individuals (416 staff and 59 students) from six schools dedicated to children with IDD

THE POPULATION

- Student participants identified as the following: **24% Black/ African American, 58% White Non-Hispanic, and 10% multiracial.**
- Most student participants and half of staff participants had at least one underlying health condition.
- Staff participants identified as the following: **15% Black/African American and 78% White Non-Hispanic.**

KEY FINDINGS

- **19 staff and 2 students tested positive for COVID-19.** Only 1 of the staff cases was traced back to the school. Researchers were not able to determine where the students were exposed to COVID-19.
- The COVID-19 positivity rates among staff and students in the six schools was not higher than the community rates. **The highest weekly positivity rate was 1.2% across all 6 schools,** which was less than area community positivity rates.

MEASURES & OBSERVATIONS

- Masks were mandated at all schools participating in the study. **Students and staff wore masks 75-100% of the time.** This masking rate was higher than expected for students with IDD.
- Many children with severe autism were rarely able to mask.
- Schools practiced social distancing, reduced class size, cleaned frequently, and opened classroom windows. No school upgraded ventilation systems.
- Researchers collected saliva samples weekly to test for COVID-19. **7,289 COVID-19 tests were performed over the 24 weeks.**

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Commitment to masking, social distancing, reduced class size, and cleaning reduce in-school spread of COVID-19.
- Screening testing may reduce in-school COVID-19 transmission by identifying people who mistake mild symptoms like runny nose for allergies.
- **Researchers encourage easy access to no cost testing at schools.**

This summary was completed in March 2022. This summary includes only results from one single study. Other studies may find different results. The study was supported by the NIH RADx® Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) initiative (Grant P50HD103525-01S1).

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To read the published research article, visit radx-up.org.

A Research Collaboration with

The COMPASS-T project is a joint partnership between the Washington University in St. Louis Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities Research Center (WUIDDRC), the University of Missouri-Kansas City Institute of Human Development, the Kennedy Krieger Institute in Maryland, and the Special School District of St. Louis County (SSD) in Missouri.